

The Ideal Hospital Room

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The project is focusing on the ideal hospital room for patients as well as the staff of the hospital. The vision is to provide, by healing architecture, a good, healing environment for the patients so e.g. the hospitalization time for the patient is reduced, and to provide a good and comfortable work environment for the staff.

Several studies have shown that patients and staff feel more comfortable if the daylight and artificial light has a certain intensity and that the indoor climate provides a certain comfort. To achieve the results above, the following things have been considered:

- Optimization of facades in terms to visibility, daylight and shadows
- Optimization of the indoor climate
- Optimization of interior of the hospital room, artificial light and acoustics.

Therefore the project has been design to find the most optimal size and location for windows and shades, so patients and staff get the best everyday stimulations.

Furthermore the project has tried to achieve the best and most stimulated color spectrum of the artificial light and the lowest possible reverberation time.

In terms of the indoor climate the integration of personalized ventilation in textiles has been researched. Furthermore, studies of floor heating and ceiling cooling have been made referring to optimization of the indoor climate at the hospital room.